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It's Not Easy Being Green – The Challenge of Having Poisonous Arsenic Containing Books in a National Library Collection

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ABSTRACT

Poisonous books in library collections with public access pose a specific challenge due to the fact that library staff and readers handle collection items intensely. This article describes the quest of the KB National Library of the Netherlands in how to deal specifically with arsenic used in colorants for library materials. It addresses the challenges of not knowing which collection items contain poisonous arsenic components, whether or not their presence constitutes a health risk, as well as dealing with official hygiene laws and regulations in handling arsenic. It describes two lines of research carried out by the library: one addressing the potential exposure to arsenic when handling these items and the other identifying arsenic containing items in the collections. The overall results of the exposure research do not show a direct link between increased arsenic levels found in the biomonitoring study and the work environment (at this specific library, at the time of testing). However, arsenic was found on work surfaces and tools used while handling arsenic containing objects. Legal health and safety regulations stipulate strict hygiene measures, which at first glance appear somewhat paradoxical to the outcome of the exposure study. Libraries have the duty to implement hygiene measures to ensure safe handling of these materials by staff and readers. The article describes the quest of the KB National Library of the Netherlands in dealing with books containing arsenic and will discuss the specific challenge and possible opportunity of the upcoming relocation of the entire collection to a new external robotized storage facility.

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bibliotoxicology; poisonous
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Introduction

The KB National Library of the Netherlands (henceforth referred to as KB) collects every publication (book, periodical, and newspaper) that appears in or about the Netherlands. The physical collections measure over 121 linear km and contain special collections of over half a million items including medieval and later manuscripts, printed books from the fifteenth to the nineteenth centuries, and unique and rare books from later periods. The collection is currently preserved in climate-controlled stacks with fixed shelving. The library is in the process of building a new external robotized storage facility for the entire collection, housed in a building where the climate will be controlled passively (Boersma et al. 2022). The presence of poisonous materials in the collection adds a large scale and time restricted challenge to the move of the collection to this new facility. At several stages in the upcoming years all collection items will be handled. This will happen during the preparation for the move (cleaning, barcoding, packing of vulnerable items, and conservation), the relocation from the current stacks to the new facility, and during the

ingest of each individual item in the automated storage and retrieval system.

The conservation department at the KB was first alerted to the potential presence of arsenic in the collection by the publication of the findings of arsenic containing green paint used in the binding of three sixteenth and seventeenth century books in the Herlufsholm Special Collection of the University Library of Southern Denmark (Holck and Rasmussen 2018; Delbey 2019). This type of binding strongly resembled books present in the KB special collections. The Covid period with several lockdowns and restricted access to the collections initially prevented further investigation into this matter. Also, the KB did not have the means to analyse the presence of arsenic in the suspected bindings. Even so, in July 2021 the staff members that potentially handle these books were informed and the first precautionary measures were taken. This included wrapping several suspected items in acid free covers to prevent direct contact as well as wearing personal protective equipment when handling them. The items were also labeled as potentially toxic with a referral to a conservator for further assistance.

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Organizational crisis management approach

Initial research at the KB into the scale of the challenge (refer to sections Testing for arsenic in the KB collections and Test results for arsenic in the KB collections) created an understanding that an unknown but potentially considerable portion of over half a million library items might contain poisonous arsenic compounds. This prospect was rather daunting, and in July 2023 a taskforce was established to tackle this challenge using a crisis management approach. This is a strategic approach which allows organizations to efficiently respond to a critical event by identifying the scale and the resources necessary to reduce the impact, as well as dealing with communication and employee well-being. This ensured that priority was given to the topic, with dedicated staff time from directly involved departments (HR, corporate communication, and collection care), chaired by a directory board member. In structured meetings using known crisis management tools such as situational reports (sitreps), the current status of knowns and unknowns was reported, a list of actions logged (to do, ongoing, and completed), and issues prioritized.

As a result from the first sitreps, the KB felt compelled to investigate whether the presence of arsenic compounds in the collection constitutes a health risk for staff who are regularly in direct contact with these items. Since collection care staff, conservators, curators, photographers, and reading room staff work with these kinds of materials on a daily basis, they were considered to be potentially at greater risk than other staff members and users of the collection, whose contact with these kinds of materials is considered to be more haphazard.

The KB decided to assess the potential risk by conducting an arsenic exposure study, to determine if arsenic finds a way into the bodies of staff members who are in regular and direct contact with this kind of material. These studies are always workplace and task specific – previous results from similar studies in other institutions can be informative but may not be considered exemplary (Bruns, Helmkamp, and Sindt 2023). Whether employees have certain health issues that could be related to the potential exposure of arsenic is not investigated in such an exposure study.

In the meantime, based on research and experience of others (initially through contact with the Cologne Institute of Conservation Sciences (CICS), and later also through the Bibliotoxicology Working Group), additional health and safety measures were implemented at the KB. These consisted of isolating items that were tested positively for arsenic from direct contact by packing them in acid free boxes made to size using the KB's Kasemake-CXD Library and Archive Grand Pro box cutting machine. These

boxes were subsequently labeled with warning stickers and handling instructions. Furthermore, library staff working with physical collections were given health and safety instructions when handling these items, which consisted of using personal protection equipment (nitrile gloves and FFP3 mask) as well as using disposable paper on work surfaces. These measures were extended to readers requesting access to library materials that had been positively identified.

Arsenic exposure study at the KB

In October 2023, the KB conducted what proved to be its first arsenic exposure study. We tested the urine of a test group, consisting of employees who work with our special collections most often and have done so for a considerable time. We also had a control group of employees who do not work with the collection at all, as a reference. All employees participated in the research out of their own free will. The set-up and results of this first study, in which urine samples were only tested for the presence of total arsenic, showed that an important opportunity was missed. The urine samples that tested positive on total arsenic were not analysed in more detail regarding the potential source of arsenic. The presence of arsenic found in several urine samples could therefore not be linked to a specific source. Several food products such as (shell) fish and rice, also contain arsenic and this may have had an impact on the results of the urine tests.

Air sampling during the handling of the collection was also conducted, but several of the gathered samples were invalid because of errors made in sampling time. Surface samples were also taken – these results are discussed further on in Results from arsenic exposure study. In March 2024, a second arsenic exposure study was therefore undertaken. This article will describe this second study in more detail. Lessons learned from both studies are shared in order to help other institutions that intend to conduct similar research.

The exposure research set-up

Employees working on a daily basis with the KB's special collections – the part of the collection roughly dating up until the nineteenth century and is considered to have the highest ratio of arsenic containing items – were invited to partake in the study. This included employees working in the special collections storage and reading room, curators, conservators, inventory controllers, and catalogers. Participation was voluntary and 13 employees partook in the second test, as well as four colleagues who do not work with the physical collection at all, to function as a control group.

The research was carried out by occupational hygienists from a commercial consultancy and secondment agency in the field of working conditions and quality. The KB's occupational physician and two occupational physicians in training, from the same external company, were involved to interpret the potential health risks for KB staff. The study ran for four days, from Monday through Thursday 4–7 March 2024.

In order to understand the specific choices that were made in the study, it is important to share the reasoning of the occupational hygienists, which forms the basis of the analysis. Together with the occupational physicians, the occupational hygienists, and the participants it was decided to conduct this study without personal protection measures (gloves and respiratory protection). In this way, the potential of arsenic entering the body during the execution of tasks involving arsenic containing collection items could be best assessed. The decision to conduct the study in this way was not taken lightly, since arsenic is a known poison. A risk assessment weighing the short duration of the test period (four days) and the fact that arsenic is present in the collection in the form of colorants of library materials, made this risk acceptable. Standard health and safety regulations – prescribing thoroughly washing your hands before and after handling the collection – still applied.

During the test week employees logged their specific tasks working with the collection, to help with the interpretation of the results. In each task it was ensured that known arsenic containing items were handled.

To determine whether there is a health risk related to working with arsenic containing collections through either direct contact or inhalation, the study measured the potential level of exposure to arsenic using three methods: biomonitoring, and air and surface sampling. Test results were compared to known threshold values. Individual test results were only revealed to the staff member in question. The results of the study were anonymously shared with the KB.

Types of arsenic and relative health risks

Both organic and inorganic arsenic compounds occur in nature. Inorganic arsenic is most common, especially in compounds with sulfur, oxygen, and chlorine. Inorganic arsenic is more harmful for humans than organic arsenic – inorganic arsenic is carcinogenic, unlike organic arsenic. Examples of inorganic arsenic are arsenic trioxide (As_2O_3 with trivalent arsenic, As^{3+} , also referred to as As III) and arsenic pentoxide (As_2O_5 with pentavalent arsenic, As^{5+} , also referred to as As V). Trivalent and pentavalent arsenic occur in both organic and inorganic chemistry. Certain foods can make a significant contribution to inorganic arsenic exposure, such as rice, grain-based products

(more specifically wheat bread), and milk and other dairy products (Laar and Griend 2024).

Examples of organic arsenic compounds are: monomethylarsonic acid $\text{CH}_3\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$ (MMA), used as a fungicide; arsenobetaine and arsenocholine, common in fish and mushrooms; derivatives of phenylarsonic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$), used as nutritional supplements for livestock; arsenic bound to carbohydrates, often referred to as arseno-sugars, mainly found in seaweed (Laar and Griend 2023).

Arsenic found in the KB collections is thought to derive from the use of green colorants such as copper acetoarsenite ($\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 3\text{Cu}(\text{AsO}_2)_2$), also known as Paris green or Schweinfurt green. Other sources could be of mineral origin such as orpiment (arsenic trisulfide As_2S_3 , As^{3+}) used in a yellow colorant, or realgar, an arsenic sulfide mineral (As_4S_4 , As^{2+}) providing an orange-red colorant (Laar and Griend 2024).

Biomonitoring

Per participant three urine samples were taken to establish a base line and the potential exposure to arsenic whilst working with the collection. One sample was taken at the beginning and one at the end of the first workday, followed by the last sample at the end of the last workday. Urine samples were analysed for total arsenic. In cases where arsenic levels were found, further analysis of arsenic metabolites (conversion or metabolic products) were carried out to help determine the source of arsenic. Arsenic detected in urine can come from other sources, such as several food products, as well as through exposure from contaminated soil or environment. Participating staff were therefore voluntarily requested to abstain from eating these known food sources over the weekend before the test week, as well as avoid certain activities such as gardening or woodworking. Participants recorded their food intake up to three days before as well as during the test week to help with the interpretation of the results.

The following threshold and reference values apply to arsenic and arsenic metabolites (conversion or metabolic products) in the urine (Table 1). Threshold values are toxic values at which the substance can have a negative effect on the body. Reference values are values found in 90% of the population. Since the Netherlands does not have legal threshold values for metabolites, those used in Germany were applied (MAK- und BAT-Werte-Liste 2023).

The most likely arsenic variants present in a library collection would be As^{3+} (As III) and As^{5+} (As V) related to the use of arsenic pigments as colorants. Monomethylarsonic acid (MMA) and dimethyl arsenate (DMA) are compounds that are formed in the body for the purpose of excretion via urine. Arsenobetaine

Table 1. Threshold and reference values of total arsenic and arsenic metabolites (conversion or metabolic products) used in the study.

Substance	Threshold value	Reference values
Total arsenic (Laar and Griend 2023)	665 nmol/l 505 nmol/g creatinine	<200 nmol/l <160 nmol/g creatinine
Arsenic trioxide (As ₂ O ₃ with trivalent arsenic, As ³⁺)	0.5 µg/l	<15.96 nmol/l
Arsenic pentoxide (As ₂ O ₅ with pentavalent arsenic, As ⁵⁺)	0.5 µg/l	<15.96 nmol/l
MMA (Monomethylarsonic acid)	2 µg/l	<29.3 nmol/l
DMA (Dimethyl arsenate)	10 µg/l	<191.5 nmol/l
Arsenobetaine		<2075nmol/l
Sum of As ³⁺ , As ⁵⁺ , MMA, DMA	10 µg/l	

derives from fish and fish products and is not found in library collections (Laar and Griend 2024).

The samples were submitted for analysis to a medical laboratory. The analysis was performed as total arsenic by means of inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), conforming to NIOSH 8310 (NIOSH 1994). Urine samples with a total arsenic value higher than 10 µg/l were further analysed for the presence of arsenic metabolites As³⁺, As⁵⁺, MMA, DMA, and arsenobetaine.

Air sampling

Air sampling was done following NEN-EN 689:2018 (NEN-EN 689:2018 1995 Workplace exposure – Measurement of exposure by inhalation to chemical agents – Strategy for testing compliance with

occupational exposure limit values 1995). Five employees were equipped with personal air sampling pumps for carrying out personal measurements whilst performing a specific task. Additionally, five air measurements were carried out stationary, placed nearby the work area (Figure 1). In this way, insight could be gained into the level of exposure through the air by visitors and other employees who may be present in the vicinity of a staff member handling arsenic containing library materials. Sampling took place with Mixed Cellulose Membrane (MCE) filters. The pumps were set to approximately 2100 ml/min. The sampling time was as long as possible during the execution of the work.

The samples were analysed for the presence and the amount of arsenic found. Exposures have been tested against the threshold value for arsenic in the air in the working environment which is 0.28 µg/m³ for an eight-hour exposure over 40 working years. This is 4–70 times more strict when compared to other European countries.

Surface sampling

Wipe samples were taken by the occupational hygienist (wearing nitrile gloves) from potentially contaminated working surface areas and tools used in handling arsenic containing objects. Samples were taken by swiping a grid of 10 × 10 cm with a Ghost Wipe™ (a specific pre-treated cloth), following

Figure 1. Curators handling special collections during the exposure research, while air samples are taken. (Photo: Henk Raap).

Method 9102 (Method 9102, Issue 1: Elements on Wipes 2023). These wipes were not used to collect samples from collection items – for this purpose an arsenic test kit was deployed (refer to Testing for arsenic in the KB collections). The wipe sample was collected in a sealed plastic container and subsequently analysed for the presence of arsenic according to the ICP-MS method. There is no threshold value – samples were either positive or negative.

Results from arsenic exposure study

Biomonitoring

The results indicate that the threshold and reference values for total arsenic in urine is exceeded several times by more than one participant (including the control group). It is noteworthy that this occurs also in the first sample taken at the start of the work week. Subsequent analysis did not find values exceeding the threshold or reference values for As^{3+} and As^{5+} . The presence of arsenic metabolites indicates in some instances that arsenobetaine and/or DMA is the likely source of the increased values. This may be related to the intake of fish and other arsenic containing foods. The organic compound arsenobetaine is found in some marine foods such as fish and algae and is considered a non-toxic form of the organoarsenic compound. The recorded menu data also reveals the intake of potentially arsenic containing food sources in these cases. In other cases where the total arsenic threshold was surpassed, further analysis for arsenic metabolites shows that no other threshold values are exceeded. A possible explanation is that the high arsenic value is caused by the arsenobetaine, for which a higher reference value has been established and the measured values were below this. No threshold value has been established for arsenobetaine.

Air sampling

The results were interpreted following NEN-EN 689:2018 1995, which assumes compliance (not exceeding threshold values) (Table 2) (NEN-EN 689:2018 1995 Workplace exposure – Measurement of exposure by inhalation to chemical agents – Strategy for testing compliance with occupational exposure limit values 1995). When the threshold value is exceeded, there is non-compliance (color red). For values lower than the threshold value but greater than the test value of 10% for three measurements or 15% for four measurements, there is still non-compliance (color orange) and additional measurements will have to be taken to demonstrate that the exposure situation is compliant. Values lower than the threshold value and lower than the test value indicate a compliant exposure situation (color green). The levels of arsenic found in the air samples remained below the legal threshold value.

Surface sampling

The first exposure study revealed that several samples tested positive for arsenic, indicating arsenic contamination (Laar and Griend 2023). As the surface samples taken in the first exposure study were valid, these are included in the overall results (Table 3). They also resulted in an improved hygiene protocol for cleaning work surfaces, which was in place during the second exposure study. As a result, special measures were introduced to reduce the risk of arsenic contamination. These include working on a disposable paper sheet in the reading room to cover work surfaces and wiping work surfaces and tools after working with collections. These measures were in place when conducting the second exposure study. The results of this study demonstrated that they had a positive effect, but that such hygiene protocols have to be further implemented in all work processes (Laar and Griend 2024).

Interpretation of all results

The urine samples of the second exposure study indicated that several employees from both the test and the control group contained heightened levels of total arsenic. However, these appear to be influenced

Table 2. Results from air sampling.

#	Type of sampling Location	Measurement (mg/m ³)	Legal threshold (mg/m ³)	% of threshold
1	On person Info desk special collection Reading room	<0.000112	0.00028	<40%
2	Stationary Info desk special collection Reading room	<0.000267	0.00028	<95%
3	Stationary Info desk special collection Reading room	<0.000174	0.00028	<62%
4	On person Conservation studio, Conservation work	<0.000222	0.00028	<79%
5	On person Conservation studio	<0.000175	0.00028	<63%
6	Stationary Conservation studio fume hood Testing for arsenic	<0.000175	0.00028	<63%
7	On person Special collection stacks	<0.000262	0.00028	<94%
8	On person Special collection stacks	<0.000263	0.00028	<94%
9	Stationary Special collection stacks	<0.000098	0.00028	<35%
10	Stationary Office space – logistics hub at coat rack with dust coats	<0.000149	0.00028	<53%

Table 3. Results from surface sampling (positive test results in bold).

Location	Measurement (mg/cm ²)
First exposure study 2023	
Cataloguing special collections – safe	<0.00010
Floor at the entrance of special collections stacks	<0.00010
Cataloguing special collections – table top	<0.00010
Stacks at Kasemake-CXD digital book measure device	<0.00010
Conservation studio – table top	0.00028
Special collections stacks – laptop	<0.00010
Special collections stacks – book cart	0.00027
Special collections stacks – barcode scanner	0.00014
Special collection reading room – collection safe	<0.00010
Special collection colloquium room – table top	<0.00010
Special collections stacks – cushion on work space	<0.00010
Special collection reading room – scales	<0.00010
Special collection reading room – cushion on table 5	0.00014
Photographic studio – photography table top	<0.00010
Second exposure study 2024	
Special collections stacks – barcode scanner	<0.0010
Special collections stacks – book cart	0.0026
Special collections stacks – door handle	<0.0010
Conservation studio – table top	<0.0010
Special collection reading room – table top 7	<0.0010
Special collections stacks – right arm sleeve of dust coat worn by employee	<0.0010
Special collections stacks – work area for inventory controllers	<0.0010
Special collections stacks – work area for inventory controllers	<0.0010
Special collection reading room – table top info desk	<0.0010
Special collection colloquium room – table top after book presentation	<0.0010

by the intake of certain foods. In most cases there was a decreasing trend in the level of total arsenic from the first sample to the last sample in the test week. Subsequent analysis did not find values exceeding the threshold or reference values for As³⁺ and As⁵⁺. Based on these findings it is not likely that the increased arsenic levels in the urine of both members of the test group and the control group are related to the work they perform in the KB National Library of the Netherlands. Please note: this conclusion can only be drawn for the KB, and only for those workspaces and specific tasks that were included in the test.

It also does not mean that there is no risk of arsenic poisoning, since arsenic was found on work surfaces and tools used while handling arsenic containing objects. It is feasible that arsenic can also transfer to one's hands while working with arsenic-containing collections. Without proper hygiene measures, there is a real risk that this contamination could be transferred to the human body, causing a health risk. Therefore, using personal protection equipment (nitrile gloves) when working with arsenic-containing collection items is necessary, as well as always washing your hands before and after using the collection.

Based on the results of the air measurements – all values are below both the threshold and the reference

value – it is concluded that at the time of the measurements arsenic and its metabolites did not spread through the air. The advice of the occupational hygienists to use a face mask for personal protection while working with arsenic-containing collection is therefore no longer mandatory but voluntary (Laar and Griend 2024).

Most importantly, arsenic is marked as a carcinogenic, mutagenic, and reprotoxic substance (Ministerie van Sociale Zaken en Werkgelegenheid 2024). This means that the KB is legally bound to ensure that exposure to an arsenic-containing collection is kept as low as possible in accordance with the ALARA principle (Laar and Griend 2024). ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) is a safety principle designed to minimize radiation doses and releases of radioactive materials. Superimposed on working with arsenic containing collections, this means that proper workplace hygiene and appropriate personal protection when working with books that may contain arsenic are strongly advised at all times.

The KB is legally bound to record the individual urine test results in the medical files of the participating employees for up to 40 years. This is because arsenic is marked as a carcinogenic substance. Furthermore, the KB is advised to repeat all tests regularly. Based on NEN-EN 689 (NEN-EN 689:2018 1995 Workplace exposure – Measurement of exposure by inhalation to chemical agents – Strategy for testing compliance with occupational exposure limit values 1995) and the air samples results, the KB is advised to repeat the study every 36 months and sooner if the work situation changes.

Lessons learned

The study into the health risks for staff and visitors of the library related to working with arsenic containing collection items was challenging. Not only did the KB never before conduct such a type of study, it was also a subject that created a whole range of responses from the employees. These varied from acting tough ('I've worked with this collection all my working life and nothing happened'), to fear or anxiety and not wanting to work with these collection items at all anymore.

We relied on the expertise of the external occupational hygienists and the occupational physicians, for whom this type of research question in a library setting, working with cultural heritage, was also novel. This meant that the KB had to be very much involved in designing the study, especially in terms of the tasks and work areas, as well as in supervising the test weeks. There was some confusion about the threshold and reference values and standards which were used. These can vary per country and are sometimes not available in one's own country or only

relating to different lines of work. It also did not become clear until halfway through the analysis of the first study that only testing for total arsenic would not provide useful answers. By that time, urine samples already tested for total arsenic were destroyed. One member of the control group handled an arsenic containing collection during the first study, which invalidated this person's test results and impacted the interpretation of all results.

In hindsight it was very unfortunate that the first study was inadequate in providing the necessary insights for the external experts to advise the library, and for the KB to act appropriately. Communication about the first study results was not according to what was agreed (an anonymized report interpreting all findings with advice on how to act). Instead, initial results were shared with contact members from the taskforce, resulting in stress and confusion.

As a result, the first study and its outcomes came across to staff as amateurish. However, throughout the entire period the KB maintained its stance on voluntary participation and open communication. Even though there was some loss of good will to participate a second time, the turnout for the second study was still high enough to be meaningful.

The scientific reports were difficult to read and had to be translated by the communication officer of the library into more accessible information using layman's terms before sharing with the participants.

The main lessons learned were:

- Carefully select a research agency and arrange guidance from the occupational physician.
- Carefully investigate in advance which threshold and reference values apply and how long air sampling tests must be taken for them to be valid.
- Establish a clear assignment: testing for arsenic trioxide and pentoxide and their associated metabolites is crucial; exclude other potential sources of arsenic that can influence the measurements as much as possible by sharing voluntary behavioral and dietary rules before and during the study.
- Ensure that members of the control group do not come into contact with the collection during the test period.
- Establish and adhere to agreed lines of communication and defined roles and responsibilities.
- Clear, open, and accessible communication is paramount.
- Participation to this kind of study has to be completely voluntary.
- Ensure careful compliance with the privacy legislation rules from all involved – for this study the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) applies (GDPR.EU 2024).

Testing for arsenic in the KB collections

Since the KB does not have a fully equipped science laboratory with analytical equipment – although it has a proper fume hood – the search was on for an arsenic test kit to help with the identification. Through contact with Prof. Dr. Andrea Renate Pataki-Hundt, at the Faculty of Cultural Sciences of the Cologne Institute of Conservation Sciences (CICS), KB conservation staff was introduced in April 2022 to the MQuandt™ arsenic test kit. This test was originally developed to analyse arsenic in aqueous samples. It was successfully deployed by CICS to identify arsenic in dry swab samples taken from the surface of arsenic containing surfaces (Wetten 2021; Wetten, Börngen, and Pataki-Hundt 2022; Wetten et al. 2024). The presence of arsenic (As^{3+} or As^{5+}) in a sample is indicated a by color change, that ranges from yellow to brown. Using a dry cotton swab, a section of a suspected book is wiped. Testing is then conducted in the fume hood, wearing nitrile gloves. The sample is added to water with reagent As-1 (a tartaric acid to acidify the water) in a test tube. A second reagent As-2 (zinc powder) is added, which forms arsenic gas if arsenic is present in the sample. A special indicator strip is positioned in the lid above the solution and the test tube is sealed. After 20 minutes, the color change of the strip indicates the presence of arsenic. Due to delivery challenges with MQuandt®, the KB resorted to Quantofix® Sulfit, another similar arsenic test. Both tests are not quantitative, but the intensity of the color is an indication of the amount of arsenic present in the swab.

The validity of the test kit was cross checked with portable XRF measurements using a Bruker Tracer 5i carried out in July 2023 by the Cultural Heritage Agency of the Netherlands (Harteveld 2023) (Figure 2). In addition, it allowed for a comparison of the two techniques in terms of practical deployment and for giving insight into the research question of which of the two techniques would be more suitable to use in a large scale operation, scanning more than half a million collection items.

The XRF spectra confirmed the findings of the arsenic test kit (Table 4). Furthermore, XRF has the potential to reveal more on the specific source of arsenic by including the presence of other components in the analysis. For example, in the case of copperacetoarsenite pigment (Schweinfurter green, $3\text{Cu}(\text{AsO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$) the spectra would also show copper. In the case of realgar or orpiment (As_2S_3 , As_2S_2 , As_4S_4 or As_2S_3) the presence of sulfur alongside arsenic would be a clear indication (Harteveld 2023).

In terms of deployment: the time to spot measure an individual book in different locations using XRF and analysing the spectra proved to be comparable

Figure 2. XRF measurements carried out on KB collection by Guusje Hartevelde (RCE). (Photo: Henk Raap).

to the time it takes to use the arsenic identification test to spot test the same areas. Both were carried out in the conservation studio, meaning additional logistics fetching the books from and returning them to the stacks. It is feasible that XRF could be used more efficiently if it could be deployed in an assembly line, possibly inside the stacks. This still has to be explored further. Both techniques have their challenges: the test kit has to be conducted in a fume hood and produces poisonous waste material (which has to be discarded as chemical waste), whereas the use of an XRF, using X-ray technology, is bound by legal health and safety regulations and requires a trained user.

Test results for arsenic in the KB collections

By July 2024, conservators tested 1520 books using 2225 arsenic test kits. 542 books tested positive. These items were selected as potentially containing arsenic by visual examination from the daily flow of collection requests and those available in the open stacks in the reading rooms. In order to gain some statistical insight into the potential challenge, all items on several shelves of special collection items in the stacks were tested. The findings raised the level of concern in the library: it showed a wider time period than the nineteenth century (Tedone and Grayburn 2022; Vermeulen et al. 2023; University of Delaware 2024; Potenziell arsenhaltiges Bibliotheksgut in der

Universitätsbibliothek und den Fachbibliotheken der CAU n.d.), with the earliest book in the KB collection containing arsenic dating from the second half of the eleventh century and the most recent from 1958. In addition, the results showed a great variety in the visual appearance of the books testing positive for arsenic, including: green to yellow, brown and almost black leather bindings; marbled leather; yellow, green, or blue colored edges of book blocks, as well as marbled, sprinkled edges; single-coloured papers as well as decorated and marbled paper used on bindings and as endleaf; lettering labels; and textile ribbons (Figure 4). When an object has tested positive for arsenic, no matter where it is found, it is marked and given a protective box (Figure 3). The call numbers of all items tested and their respective results are recorded, also when the test for arsenic is negative.

Table 4. Overview of the XRF results. Detected elements with the highest intensity are represented in bold and trace elements within brackets (Hartevelde 2023).

Object number	Analysis reference name: including object number, location and settings of measurement (measuring time (seconds), energy (kV), electrical current (uA), spot size (mm))	Detected elements
10J29	Test_10J29_Front cover painted part_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Ca Fe S Pb K (Cu) (Si) (Cr) (Mn) (Zn) (Ti) (Al)
1775D138	Test_1775D138_Blue rear cover relief left_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Ca Pb (K) (Cu) (Cr) (Ti) (Zn)
1775D138	Test_1775D138_Blue rear cover relief right_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Ca (Pb) (K) (Cu) (Ti) (Cr) (Zn) (Al)
1775D138	Test_1775D138_Blue paper on back board close to the back_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Cu Ca (K) (Pb) (S) (Zn) (Ti) (Cr) (Al) (Si)
1775D138	Test_1775D138_Blue paper on back board close to the back_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Ca K (Pb) (Cu) (S) (Cr) (Ti) (Zn) (Al) (Si)
1775D138	Test_1775D138_Blue paper on back board close to the back_60s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Ca K (Pb) (Cu) (S) (Cr) (Ti) (Zn) (Al) (Si)
1B9	Test_1B9_Leather on front cover_10s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe As Ca S Cu K Cr (Ti) (Ba) (P) (Al)
1B9	Test_1B9_Leather on front cover_20s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Fe Ca S Pb As Cu K Cr Ba (Ti) (Zn) (Al)
1B9	Test_1B9_Top edge_10s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	As Ca Fe S K (Cr) (Mn) (Ti) (Si) (Zn) (Al)
2H22	Test_2H22_Velvet middle of front cover_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Ca Fe K S Cr (Pb) (As) (Mn) (Ti) (Al)
2H22	Test_2H22_Velvet front cover under missing fittings_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Ca Fe K Cu S Cr (Pb) (As) (Mn) (Ti) (Si) (Al)
760j10	Test_760j10_Bottom edge_10s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	As Ca S Fe K Co Ar Ba Ni (Si) (Cr) (Cu)
760j10	Test_760j10_Cut tail_20s_40kV_8uA_3 mm	As Ca S Fe K Ba (Si) (Cr)
760j10	Test_760j10_Bottom edge_20s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	As Ca S Fe K Co Ba (Si) (Cr) (Mn) (Al)
760j10	Test_760j10_Bottom edge_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	As Ca S Fe K (Ba) (Si) (Cr) (Al)
Background	Test_Background paper_40s_40kV_8uA_8 mm	Ti (Fe) (Ca) (Cr)

Figure 3. Positively tested collection item with its box made to measure. (Photos: KB Beeldstudio).

In this way it can be easily checked if in future it is again visually identified as a potential candidate.

As a result, there is an indication that the ratio of arsenic containing books in the collection is possibly much higher than previously assumed, as is also reported in the progress report by the University Library Kiel, referencing the findings of the KEK-Modellprojekt 'Grüne Bände aus der ULB Bonn', in which about 50% of the 300 volumes examined contained arsenic (Bruns, Helmkamp, and Sindt 2023). This could mean that the portion of the KB collections in which arsenic could be found can extend to over half a million library identifiers or call numbers, with approximately 35% potentially containing arsenic. Adding to the concern is the experience that it is very difficult, if not impossible, to visually identify arsenic containing colorants.

Further challenges

At first glance, the outcome of the exposure study and the legal health and safety regulations might appear somewhat paradoxical. The exposure study did not establish a correlation between arsenic compounds found in biomonitoring and the work performed by the tested persons during the test period. Air sampling did not indicate that arsenic compounds are present in the air. However, surface testing demonstrated the presence of arsenic on some surfaces that had been in contact with arsenic containing books, justifying the use of health and safety measures. In the Netherlands, the KB has the duty to implement hygiene measures to ensure safe handling of these materials by staff and readers. The ALARA principle has to be followed. However, implementing this principle in practice is not easy. The library has many different workflows in which a collection is handled. With the cut-off date of 1950s, all workflows are affected, not just those related to our special collections. This also

includes workflows that extend beyond the KB, such as large-scale digitization projects that involve other libraries and external digitization companies. As the collection is handled by readers, a workable, safe, and legal process for handling requests has also to be designed. In order to establish rapport and compliance with these measures, staff has to be included in designing hygiene protocols that are practical in each workflow. Staff must be regularly trained and supervised to follow health and safety measures.

Materials necessary for the protocols have to be budgeted for and kept in stock, as well as the proper handling of waste materials that has to be implemented. The positively tested items in the collection show a much wider range of dates and appearances of arsenic containing books. Additionally, it has proven extremely difficult if not impossible to visually identify arsenic containing colorants. At present the KB only has the capacity to test those items visually selected as suspicious by staff in the daily flow of collection handlings. In order to improve the catch rate, staff working with collections on a daily basis have been provided with a visual tool as well as training on the job (Figure 4).

It is now assumed that arsenic could be present in a significant part of the collection dating up to the 1950s. Well over half a million of items would have to be checked to identify all items. In scaling up the research, the KB wishes to include other poisonous materials already identified in the Bibliotoxicology Working Group such as chrome, mercury, and lead. It is also not known whether the collection might contain the remains of early pesticides, and this would have to be added to a full scale collection scan for poisonous materials.

The KB is exploring the possibility to scale up the research, including other poisonous materials mentioned above. Conducting the research in the stacks, preferably with analysing collections at shelf level,

Arsenic, you can't judge a book by its cover

Figure 4. Visual tool to help staff identify suspected items. (Photos: KB Beeldstudio).

would narrow down the number of items that have to be analysed individually. At present the KB does not have the capacity nor the means to carry out such a large-scale investigation. The KB can only use the test kit to identify arsenic containing collections, as it does not have a handheld XRF nor the staff qualified to operate it.

There is huge time pressure, as the library is preparing to move its entire collection to a new external storage facility. The rehousing is planned to take two years, roughly from 2027 to 2029. Even though this seems to be a daunting task, it may also be an opportunity, because all collection items are handled (some more than others depending on the state of cataloging

and preservation) in the preparation phase. This stage has already started, meaning the collection is being surface cleaned, barcoded and, in case of damaged or fragile items, packed and sometimes conserved. It may be possible to include a large scale study in the workflow.

The new storage facility is an automated storage and retrieval system, where the collection is stored inside special containers that are handled by robots (Boersma et al. 2022) This means that each collection item is permanently placed in a specific spot inside a container. Since poisonous collection items would need to be isolated using adequate packaging, it is crucial to undertake the identification and follow-up steps in advance of the move. This is in order to avoid having to adjust filled containers at a later date, as the protective packaging is bound to take up more space. For the sake of collection management, it is important to store poisonous collection items together in marked containers.

The KB is also looking to gain better understanding of the risks of handling poisonous materials in case of a disaster, such as a flood or fire. The library is currently housed in a building that no longer meets the requirements to ensure the safe storage of its collection. The KB has an up-to-date disaster plan and a fully trained collection recovery team, which has been in action several times over the last few years. However, the library is concerned for the potential risks of handling and treating wet or damp arsenic containing items, especially since only a small proportion of these items has been identified in the collection. Concerns are specifically for any unwanted chemical reactions and the spread of poisonous contaminants. These risks have to be further analysed and appropriate mitigation measures identified.

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